

Metastatic Retroperitoneal Paraganglioma: A Delicate Management

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Abstract

Introduction: Metastatic retroperitoneal paragangliomas are malignant neuroendocrine tumors (NET) of neuroectodermal origin. Although rare, their management poses many diagnostic and, above all, therapeutic difficulties.

Case report: We present the clinical observation of a 53-year-old female patient, initially treated for a paraganglioma of the right adrenal lodge. In view of the reappearance of clinical symptoms and the positivity of the biological, morphological and functional work-up, the diagnosis being in favour of a metastatic retroperitoneal paraganglioma, for which the patient was referred to oncology.

Discussion and Conclusion: Metastatic retroperitoneal paraganglioma is a rare and serious entity, and its management is complex, based on surgery in operable forms, followed by neoadjuvant treatment.

Keywords: metastatic paraganglioma, disease progression, surgery, somatostatine analogue, chemotherapy.

INTRODUCTION:

Paragangliomas are rare neuroendocrine tumors originating from neural crest cells. They are predominantly located in the head and neck, starting from the ganglia of the parasympathetic autonomic nervous system. Less frequent is the subdiaphragmatic location, originating from sympathetic ganglia. Several authors refer to them as extra-adrenal pheochromocytomas. They are exceptionally found in the retroperitoneal region, posing enormous diagnostic difficulties especially with pheochromocytomas, and therapeutic challenge when they are metastatic.

The incidence of Pheochromocytoma and Paraganglioma (PPGL) represents 2 and 8 per million, with a prevalence that ranges between 1/2500 and 1/6500 (1).

Most paragangliomas are sporadic, while 10% are familial. According to studies, almost 40% of patients with paragangliomas carry germline mutations (2).

The diagnosis of PPGL is usually made in the presence of high blood pressure which is resistant to treatment, or which occurs in a young subject. The clinical picture is dominated by the famous menard's triad, reflecting the catecholaminergic hypersecretion of functional paragangliomas. Large patient cohorts report that 35% to 40% of PGLs develop metastases (3).

We present a case of metastatic retroperitoneal paraganglioma to illustrate its diagnostical and therapeutic difficulties.

CASE REPORT:

A 53-year-old female patient, diabetic and hypertensive since 4 months, without notable familial history, admitted to the ER for hypertensive peaks of 190/100 mmhg. She reported paroxysmal attacks of headache, palpitations and profuse sweating lasting more than 3 months.

On examination a Blood Pressure (BP) of 160/95 mmhg, Heart Rate (HR) 94 bpm, Respiratory Rate (RR) 21 cpm. An abdominal ultrasound revealed a mass of the right adrenal lodge, confirmed at AbdominoPelvic Computed Tomography Scan (CT) with a tissue mass of the right adrenal lodge, slightly hypodense in spontaneous contrast (40 HU), homogeneous, with clear boundaries and regular contours and homogeneously contrast-enhanced 70 HU at 1 min and 53 HU at 10 min, measuring approximately 51*35*31 mm.

On biological examination, 24 h Urinary Methoxylates Derivatives (UMD) were largely elevated with Normetanephrines (NMN) at 130 ug/24h almost 3 times the upper limit of normal (ULN) and Metanephrine (MN) superior than 847 ug/24h (30 times ULN) with normal 24-hour creatinuria. The diagnosis of pheochromocytoma or paraganglioma was made and patient was placed on alpha blocker (doxazosine 1 mg per day) in addition to her treatment for hypertension.

The screening test for type 2 Multiple Endocrine Neoplasia (MEN 2) including phosphocalcic assessment, calcitonin and cervical ultrasound returned normal. Echocardiographic evaluation revealed left ventricular hypertrophy. After preparation, the patient underwent tumour resection with right adrenalectomy by laparoscopic surgery.

Pathological examination was in favor of a paraganglioma. The post-operative evolution was marked by the disappearance of the Menard's triad, normalization of blood glucose and blood pressure, for which the patient had to stop her antihypertensive and hypoglycemic treatment on her own, and was lost to follow-up.

After three and a half years, the patient was seen again for the reappearance of Menard's triad, with hypertensive peaks reaching 230 mmhg systolic. In view of this finding, 24 h UMD were performed, showing normal NMN at 34 ug/24h and high MN at 308 ug/24h (9.3 times ULN). An abdominal CT scan with adrenal slices and a cervicothoracic CT scan were performed, but revealed no abnormalities (Figure 1). An MRI of the adrenal glands was performed and revealed a mass in the right adrenal cavity measuring 36*26 mm, polylobed, with regular contours, hyposignal T1, hypersignal T2, heterogeneously enhanced after injection of Gadolinium, The mass contacts the undersurface of the liver and the upper pole of the right kidney, with loss of the cleavage plane, it also contacts and displaces the inferior vena cava (IVC), which is reduced in calibre but remains permeable, the left adrenal gland is thin, presence of an inter-hepato-renal ganglion measuring 8.7 mm in hypersignal diffusion.

The imaging work-up was completed by a Mono-Iodo-Benzyl-Guanidine (MIBG) scintigraphy, which revealed a retroperitoneal mass above the right kidney, measuring 3*2.9 cm, in favour of tumour recurrence, with no signs of secondary location in bone, lung or liver (Figure 2).

The decision was surgical revision. The surgical procedure involved resection of a tumour mass measuring approximately 2*2*0.6 cm with a greyish appearance, the inter-hepato-renal lymph node measuring 0.3*1.2 cm and a peritoneal nodule measuring 1.5*0.8*0.5 cm with a yellowish appearance. Anatomopathological study of the 3 samples showed a well-encapsulated tumour proliferation, with a richly vascularized alveolar and endocrinoid architecture. Cytoplasm was broadly basophilic, slightly granular and with pleiomorphic nuclei. Cell atypia was discrete and mitosis were rare (2/10 fields). Cells were arranged in trabeculae delimited by spindle-shaped cells, with no vacular emboli or tumor necrosis.

Immunohistochemical studies using immunoperoxidase (automated technique: OMNIS station, Agilent) showed: moderate to intense and diffuse cytoplasmic expression of tumor cells with anti-Synaptophysin antibody (Clone SY38, Dako), anti-Chromogranin antibody (Clone LK2H10, Dako), nuclear and cytoplasmic expression of supratentorial cells with anti-PS100 antibody (Polyclonal Rabbit, Dako), absence of tumor cell expression with anti-Cytokeratin antibody (Clone AE1/AE3, Dako). Overall, the morphological and immunohistochemical appearance was compatible with a metastatic paraganglioma (WHO classification 2022).

After the 2nd surgery, the patient was still suffering from Menard's triad, with high blood pressure and glycemia requiring her to remain on antihypertensive medication and insulin therapy. She also reported a weight loss of 7 kg over the last 3 months. The 24 h UMD were recontrolled, showing NMN at 0,47 mg/24 h (1,23 times ULN) and MN at 3,91 mg/24h (21 times ULN).

Somatostatin receptor scintigraphy (99mTc-labelled Tectrotyd octreoscan) (SSTR) coupled with SPECT/CT) performed one month post-operatively revealed a right supra-renal retroperitoneal mass measuring 2.1*1.7 cm (Figure3).

TAP CT scan performed 3 months after 2 nd surgery showed a nodular formation in the right adrenal lodge, poorly limited, spontaneously iso-dense (34UH), heterogeneously enhanced after injection of contrast, arriving in contact with the IVC measuring approximately 2.4*1.8*2.3 cm with another mass opposite the upper pole of the right kidney, with the

same radiological characteristics and measuring 1.9 * 1*0.8 cm, existence of discrete infiltration of the right peri-renal fat (Figure 4).

With this new histological and imaging finding in favour of a borderline retroperitoneal paraganglioma between a locally advanced tumour and a metastatic tumour, the medical file was presented to the RCP staff and the decision was a 3rd surgery.

During the 3rd surgery, there was the intraoperative observation of several adhesions and multiple nodules at the peritoneal, hepatic and diaphragmatic levels for which 3 biopsies were performed (Figure 5).

Anatomopathological microscopic study revealed a vascularized tumoral proliferation of endocrinoid architecture, made up of small to medium-sized, monomorphic cells, often with round, enlarged nuclei with dense, dispersed chromatin, often nucleolated and with occasional mitotic figures. Immunohistochemical complement showed positive expression of tumor cells with anti-Synaptophysin antibody, anti-Chromogranin antibody, positive expression of supratentorial cells with anti-PS100 antibody, negative expression with anti-Cytokeratin antibody and moderate expression of anti-Ki 67 antibody of around 3%. In total, it was a peritoneal, hepatic and diaphragmatic localization of the paraganglioma already diagnosed. Faced with this result, the patient was referred to oncology for therapeutic decision. The patient was started on Lanreotide 120 mg sustained-release (SOMATULIN) injected once a month because of tumor fixation on somatostatin receptor scintigraphy (octrescan).

The biological work-up was completed by measuring chromogranin A, which was very high at 890 ng/ml.

In view of this finding, a PET scan 18*F-FDG was made noting a hyper-metabolic tumour mass in the right adrenalectomy lodge, appearing to infiltrate adjacent parts of the liver and the homolateral diaphragmatic pillar, with a suspicious hyper-metabolic area in segment IV of the liver (Figure 6). Depending on the therapeutic response to somatulin, chemotherapy protocol will be discussed.

Figure 1 : Abdominal CT scan with adrenal slices.

Figure 2 : Mono-Iodo-Benzyl-Guanidine (MIBG) scintigraphy : retroperitoneal mass above the right kidney mesured 3*2.9 cm (blue arrow).

Figure 3 : OctreoScan : Right supra-renal retroperitoneal mass measuring 2.1*1.7 cm (Red arrow).

Figure 4 :TAP CT scan,(a) : nodule of right adrenal lodge (2.4*1.8*2.3 cm). (blue arrow). (b) : nodule above the upper pole of the right kidney (1.9 * 1*0.8 cm) (red arrow)

Figure 5: (a), (b), (c) and (d): laparoscopic intraoperative observation: Peritoneal, hepatic and diaphragmatic nodules (metastases). (Black arrows).

Figure 6: PET scan 18*F-FDG: hyper-metabolic tumour mass in the right adrenalectomy lodge with homolateral hepatic and diaphragmatic infiltration (intersection of the 2 red and blue lines).

DISCUSSION:

PGLs are rare neuroendocrine tumors deriving from abdominal sympathetic ganglia or encephalic and cervical parasympathetic ganglia. PGLs developed from the chromaffin cells of the adrenal medulla are known as pheochromocytomas. The annual incidence of PGLs has been estimated to be around 0.6 per 100,000 people (4).

Abdominal location is classic in PGLs, usually in the organ of Zuckerkandl at the aortic bifurcation, whereas retroperitoneal PGL is a rare entity because only two percent of PGLs are retroperitoneal.

In our patient, the paraganglioma was located in the retroperitoneum in close contact with the IVC, a location rarely reported in the literature (5). PGL occur preferentially in the 4th decade, with no predominance of either sex (6).

Genetic origin is found in 40% of cases of PGL secondary to mutations mainly in germlines genes (7,8). These tumors occur either in isolation or in syndromes, mainly associated with Von Hippel Lindau disease (VHL), neurofibromatosis type 1 (NF1) and multiple endocrine neoplasia type 2 (MEN 2). Genetic mutations in PPGL are divided into 3 groups called molecular clusters, each characterized by its mutations, molecular mechanisms and potential for malignancy and metastasis : the pseudohypoxic cluster 1 (cluster 1 A Krebs cycle-related genes with mutations SDHx, FH, MDH2, which are almost 100% germline and responsible for 4%-12% of sporadic PPGLs and Cluster 1 B VHL/EPAS1-related genes, with 25 % of this mutations are germline...), the kinase signaling cluster 2 (mutations in the rearranged-during-transfection (RET) proto-oncogene, (NF1), transmembrane protein 127 (TMEM127), Myc-associated factor X (MAX) and Wnt signaling cluster 3.

Almost 50-60% of patients with metastatic PGLs carry Cluster 1 mutations (9,10). According to a systematic retrospective study that assessed metastatic risk according to molecular cluster type: 24,3 % of patients with cluster 1 developed metastases of which 40,5 % with cluster 1A, 11 % with cluster 1B. In patients with cluster 3, 11,4% developed metastases and only 4.1% of those with cluster 2 (11).

	Cluster 1A	Cluster 1B	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
Mutations	<i>SDHx (A,B,C or D), FH, MDH2, DLST3.</i>	<i>VHL, EPAS1</i>	<i>RET, MEN2, NF1, HRAS, TMEM127</i>	<i>MAML3, CSDE1</i>
Molecular mechanisms	Krebs cycle: ADN hypermethylation. Inactivation of tumor Suppressor gene (TSG). accumulation of HIFa	Hypoxia signaling: Inactivation TSG (VHL). accumulation of HIFa. + expression of croissance factors (VEGF, PDGF), angiogenesis.	Kinase signaling: -proliferation, -chromatin remodeling, -angiogenesis, -metabolic switch to glycolysis and glutaminolysis.	Wnt signaling-related -overactivation of Wnt/Hedgehog and b-catenin. - increased angiogenesis, survival, invasion, metastasis. - deregulation of metabolism.
Metastatic risk	(SDHB +++)	(VHL++)	(MEN2B+)	(MAML3 +)

Table 1: characteristics of the various molecular clusters associated with PPGLs

The PGL can be functional (secreting) or nonfunctional. When it is secretory, catecholamine hypersecretion is responsible for a variable clinical picture ranging from the more specific Menard's triad with palpitations, headaches and sweating and uncontrolled high blood pression, to atypical presentations such as nausea, vomiting, constipation, abdominal or chest pain, sweating, anxiety, tremor and orthostatic hypotension, hyperglycemia or diabetes mellitus. Moreover, 10 to 15% paragangliomas are asymptomatic (12), especially tumors with small seize (<2 cm) by low catecholamine production or by metabolizing catecholamines without secreting them.

Our patient had no family history of PPGLs or associated hereditary syndromes, and the diagnosis of PGL was initially evoked in the face of paroxysmal Menard's triad and severe and resistant high blood pression then confirmed by very high 24 h UMD levels, particularly metanephrine. Depending on the study, normetanephrine elevation with no or minimal metanephrine elevation direct to the diagnosis of PGL cluster 1 (9,13, 14). In addition, PGLs with a noradrenergic biochemical phenotype have a higher metastatic risk than those with an adrenergic phenotype (almost a 3-fold increase in risk) (10), which reflects cluster 1 membership for the first and cluster 2 for the 2nd (15).

According to recommendations, in non-emergency situations and in the presence of any clinical suspicion of PGL, a 24-hour measurement of free plasma metanephrines and/or urinary methoxylates derivatives should be carried out prior to imaging (9). In our patient, admitted in a hypertensive emergency, abdominal imaging was required before the 24-hour UMD was carried out.

The 2nd step after biochemistry is morphological imaging, enabling tumor localization and characterization. Abdominal CT with adrenal protocol (calculation of spontaneous density, density kinetics after PDC injection, relative and absolute washout) has a high sensitivity of around 100% and a low specificity of 50% for PCCs. This sensitivity is lower for sympathetic, head and neck PGLs. The usual scannographic image of PPGL is a tissue mass, heterogeneous after contrast injection, with spontaneous density greater than 10 HU, containing areas of necrosis or hemorrhage. On the other hand, MRI is more sensitive than CTscan for detecting sympathetic PGLs (abdominal, retroperitoneal) (16,17), this was the case in our patient, when the adrenal scanno-graphic sections missed the visualization of tumor recurrence, whereas the adrenal MRI localized the tumor and the metastatic lymph node. Alongside diagnosis of the primary tumour, CT and MRI can detect metastases, with CT being superior for lung metastases and MRI for liver metastases (15).

Functional imaging provides high sensitivity and specificity in the search for multifocal lesions and/or metastases, as well as for preoperative staging of PCCs and postoperative staging of PGLs (18). Recent published guidelines for fonctionnel imaging of PPGLs recommande [68Ga]-DOTA-SSA PET/CT with high sensitivity of the order of 95 to 100% (19), if not available, [18F] FDG PET/CT may be used. The MIBG scintigraphy is the most specific functional imaging (>95%) but its sensitivity may become low for small tumors or those associated with SDHx mutations (20, 21). In our case, MIBG scintigraphy performed before the 2nd surgery showed tumoral recurrence whose size was greater than 2 cm, but did not show lymph node or peritoneal metastases. On the other hand, 99mTc-labelled Tectrotyd Octreoscan practiced 1 month after this surgery was very useful, since it allowed visualization of the tumor mass, which explains the persistence of clinical symptoms, this lesion was confirmed on abdominopelvic CT scan, which necessitated a 3rd tumor reduction surgery. the intraoperative findings during the 3rd surgery revisited almost the same lesions observed during the 2nd surgery, in particular tumour mass, hepatic, peritoneal and lymph node metastases, necessitating multiple biopsies to confirm the diagnosis of metastatic PGL.

Surgery plays a key role, especially in cases of locoregional disease. When complete tumor resection is impossible or presence of metastases, surgery to reduce tumor volume is recommended, to attenuate catecholamine secretion and slow tumor progression.

The recommendations of the US Society of Endocrinology and the European Society of Hypertension emphasize the benefit of pre-operative preparation of PPGLs by administering alpha-blockers for 7 to 14 days prior to surgery to prevent any cardiovascular crisis or emergency (9), without forgetting the need for optimal control and stability of blood pressure figures (9,22,23). The main alpha-blockers used are: phenoxybenzamine (alpha 1 and 2, non-selective and non-competitive), doxazosin (alpha 1, selective and competitive), prazosin, terazosin. Beta-blockers may be justified, especially in cases of tachyarrhythmia, but should be administered 2 or 3 days after alpha-blockers.

The discovery of somatostatin's central regulatory role in the physiology of neuroendocrine tumors has revolutionized the diagnosis and treatment of these tumors. Based on the fact that (NET) overexpress somatostatin receptors (5 subtypes from 1 to 5), the use of SST analogues has proved effective in several cases reported in the literature. In addition to their anti-secretory effect, these molecules have an interesting anti-proliferative effect. In our patient, right supra-renal hyperfixation on OcteoScan (tumour recurrence) suggested that the tumor expressed somatostatin receptors, which encouraged us to use Lanreotide as an SST analogue.

Systemic therapies play a central role in the management of metastatic retroperitoneal PGLs, and the choice of treatment depends on the progression of the disease ; Chemotherapy with the Averbuch CVD protocol: Cyclophosphamide (750mg/m²), Vincristine (1.4 mg/m²) and Dacarbazine (600 mg/m²) is the treatment of choice in cases of rapid progression and large tumour volume (9,22,24) with a disease control rate (DCR) of 48 to 100 % and a progression free survival (PFS) of 20 to 40 months (25,26). Temozolomide monotherapy can also be used, after 6 to 9 cycles of CVD or if CVD treatment is prolonged as a maintenance treatment and in less aggressive PGLs (25, 27).

On the other hand, in cases of slow to moderate disease progression, radionuclide therapy is recommended as a first-line treatment. Several studies have reported the benefits of ¹³¹I-MIBG therapy and high specific activity (HSA) ¹³¹I-MIBG in patients with a positive MIBG-scintigraphy with a DCR of 63% to 87% and a PFS of 20.6-28.5 months for ¹³¹I-MIBG and a DCR of 92 % for HSA ¹³¹I-MIBG (9,28,29). Somatostatin receptor (SSTR)- based radionuclide therapy (PRRT) with ¹⁷⁷Lu-DOTA can also be used as recommended by the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) and by the Working Group on Endocrine Hypertension of the European Society of Hypertension (9). The DCR for PPGLs with PRRT was in most retrospective studies (10/12) $\geq 80\%$ (67%-100%) and PFS was 17 to 39 months.

If the disease progresses after chemotherapy or radionuclide therapy, or if these treatments are not possible, anti-angiogenic treatments such as tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKI) (i.e sunitinib) may be a therapeutic option. A retrospective study with prospective clinical phase 2 evaluating the effect of sunitinib in patients with metastatic PGL showed DCR 57 % to 83% and PFS at 13,4 months for the prospective clinical phase (30,31).

In our patient, In the face of this dramatic diagnosis as a metastatic retroperitoneal PGL with a rapid progression (local recurrence in less than 3 months after 2ⁿ surgery) and multiple metastases, the decision taken after several multidisciplinary staff meetings is the complement to oncology treatment with the planned CVD scheme.

CONCLUSION:

Metastatic retroperitoneal PGLs are rare but serious neuroendocrine tumors, due to their catecholaminergic secretion, tumoral and metastatic invasion. Ideal management begins with tumor localization, the search for metastases and therapeutic discussion based on the progression of the disease and in the light of the latest recommendations from learned societies.

Declaration of interest:

The authors declare that they have no direct or indirect interest (financial or in kind) in any private, industrial or commercial organization related to the presented subject.

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